

EFFECT OF EMBEDDED CATALYTIC SELF-HEALING ON CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A catalytic healing agent, Sc(OTf)₃ (scandium triflate), is incorporated into fibre-reinforced polymer (FRP) specimens during hand layup. Following cure of the host material, the catalytic healing agent (CHA) is shown to remain functional and can be used to achieve effective repair in damaged specimens. The distribution of catalyst within the fracture plane of double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens is varied in order to assess the impact on pristine material properties and healing efficiency. The inclusion of this healing functionality has been shown to have no detrimental impact on pristine material fracture toughness. Following initial failure and exposure of the catalyst, delivery of an epoxy monomer and subsequent curing effects re-bonding of the fracture surfaces. While the localised nature of the catalyst leads to localised repair, full strength recovery has been achieved by repairing as little as 15% of the fracture surface.

1. INTRODUCTION

Among the three primary approaches to the implementation of self-healing in fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) materials; intrinsic healing, microencapsulation of healing agents, and the inclusion of vascular networks; to date the latter approach has dominated [1–3]. Intrinsic healing methods rely on the presence of an in-built capacity for re-bonding in the material. While the major focus has been on implementation within non-structural materials, there are examples of intrinsic healing of FRPs [4]. Microencapsulation has been used extensively to repair bulk polymer materials, but is primarily limited by the small available volume of healing agents [5]. In contrast, the vascular approach enables delivery of large volumes of healing agents, allowing for complete infusion of damage sites. Furthermore, the laminar nature of FRPs makes fabrication of 1- and 2-dimensional vascular networks relatively straightforward [6-7].

This paper considers functionalisation of prepreg material to undergo self-healing after fracture. The healing agent deployed is independent of delivery mechanism, i.e it could be utilised with either a microencapsulated or vascular approach. A demonstration is made of the inclusion of a catalytic epoxy curing agent within an FRP specimen, with the aim of showing that the catalyst is capable of being involved in a repair process after being subjected to the cure of the host material. Currently, this repair process is limited to the cure of an epoxy monomer which is injected after initial damage propagation. In the future, combination with microencapsulated healing agents, embedded within the resin pocket regions typically found within FRPs at features such as butt joints and ply drops, is envisaged.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 DCB Manufacture & Testing

Unidirectional carbon fibre / epoxy prepreg (SE70, Gurit, UK) laminates were manufactured by hand layup in preparation of Double Cantilever Beam fracture toughness specimens

(ASTM D55288 [8]). A 15 μm release film insert was used to produce an initial delamination length (a_0) of 50 mm. A Lewis Acid solid catalyst ($\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$) was added to pre-cut regions in the central ply using two different methods which are described in detail in section 3.1.1.

Laminates were cured according to the manufacturer's specifications at 100°C for 100 minutes under 1 bar pressure. Specimens were cut to size with a diamond blade and, following grit blasting of the surfaces, hinges were bonded with an epoxy adhesive. A schematic is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1: DCB geometry. Hinged specimens result in an effective initial delamination length of 50 mm. Specimens were nominally 20 mm wide. All dimensions in mm.

Testing was carried out on a Shimadzu AGS-X universal test machine with a calibrated 1 kN load cell in accordance with ASTM D 5528 [8]. The test rate was 5 mm min^{-1} . A high resolution video image capture system was used to record the delamination length during the test to an accuracy of ± 0.5 mm. Cracks were propagated for approximately 50 mm, allowing for full exposure of the embedded CHA.

Following initial fracture, epoxy monomer was delivered to the fracture surface with a syringe. Specimens were then sealed and exposed to the cure conditions (10 hours at 80°C). Repeat testing proceeded as above, but with specimens tested to failure.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Manufacture of FRP Specimens

3.1.1 Manufacturing Method

The inclusion of any additional functionality within a material ought to have minimal impact on the host material's properties. When including healing the functionality described herein, great care is taken to maintain the pristine performance of the FRP. Previous work incorporated $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ within DCB specimens by applying regions of catalyst directly to the central ply [9], as shown in Figure 2a. This method can lead to a large reduction in the fracture toughness of the DCB. In this work, the CHA was incorporated into pre-cut regions in the central two plies, as shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 2: a) 'Interleaved' catalyst. b) Catalyst added to cut plies.

Load–displacement behaviour of DCBs featuring catalyst incorporated by both of the above methods was compared to baseline SE70 behaviour, Figure 3. The green baseline trace shows typical stable crack propagation. The black interleaved catalyst trace contrasts starkly with the baseline,

featuring sharp load drops due to the reduction in fracture toughness caused by the CHA. However, when CHA is included within cut plies on the fracture plane, a return to behaviour in line with baseline performance was observed. Two small but sharp load drops can be seen in the cut plies trace, associated with a short rapid crack jump over the CHA region, before a return to normal stable crack propagation. The influence of these load drops on overall specimen toughness is well within the experimental scatter.

Figure 3: Representative load–displacement plots for DCBs comparing the two methods of catalyst inclusion with a baseline specimen.

3.1.2 Catalyst Distribution

The loading and distribution of catalyst was varied in order to maximize healing potential while maintaining pristine material performance. Figure 4 shows the catalyst distributions investigated herein, all manufactured using the cut ply method described above. In all cases there is a 10 mm separation between the end of the pre-crack and the embedded catalyst. The areal density of catalyst in each specimen type is detailed in Table 1.

The influence of varying catalyst distribution was quantified by use of the area method of DCB analysis [10]. Fracture toughness of the specimen is calculated as:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{\Delta W}{b \cdot \Delta a} = \frac{W_{ext} - W_{strain}}{b \cdot \Delta a}$$

where W_{ext} is the external work, W_{strain} the strain energy, Δa the change in delamination length and b the specimen's width.

Figure 4: Distributions of catalyst in DCB fracture planes that were investigated in this study.

It was found that the interleave method results in a significant drop in specimen fracture energy relative to baseline specimens, which contained no embedded catalyst. The cut ply method, however, achieves specimen fracture energies of similar magnitude to the baseline. Some variation in G_{IC} is seen between different catalyst distributions. Type **B** specimens, which feature the smallest areal density of embedded catalyst, show the highest fracture energy. Type **C** specimens, which incorporate catalyst along the length of the healing area, show the largest decrease in fracture energy. This is attributed to the absence of regions along the length free from the influence of embedded catalyst, which are present in all other specimen types. Type **A** specimens, which feature two 5 mm x 10 mm catalyst regions have a fracture energy very similar to the baseline performance.

Specimen Type	Healing Area / mm ²	Catalyst Area / % of healing area	Catalyst Loading / g	Pristine Fracture Energy (G_{IC}) / J m ⁻²	Peak Load Healing Efficiency (ζ_p)
Baseline	-	-	-	487 ± 55	-
A Interlaminar	600	20%	0.22	199 ± 44	-
A	600	20%	0.22	539 ± 56	133% ± 28%
B	260	2%	0.01	571 ± 68	45% ± 15%
C Cut Plies	600	13%	0.22	317 ± 130	58% ± 15%
D	600	10%	0.11	454 ± 82	75% ± 27%
E	600	15%	0.16	493 ± 95	96% ± 41%

Table 1: Details and healing efficiencies of catalyst distribution specimens.

3.2 HEALING

Previous studies have demonstrated the feasibility of curing epoxy resins with metal triflates and applied them to the repair of both bulk and fibre-reinforced polymers [11–13]. Here it is shown that $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ is capable of functioning as an epoxy cure agent after exposure to high temperatures within a host FRP.

A low-viscosity, high-toughness epoxy system [14] was used in conjunction with the catalytic curing agent. The epoxy comprises 50 wt% Epon 828, an oligomeric diglycidylether bisphenol A

(DGEBA) (Figure 5a); 30 wt% polypropylene glycol diglycidyl ether (Figure 5b) and 20 wt% HyPox RA840 (Figure 5c), a DGEBA epoxy with a carboxyl terminated acrylonitrile adduct on 19% of epoxy groups. Following injection of the monomer, healing is carried out at 80°C for 10 hours.

Figure 5: a) Diglycidylether bisphenol A (DGEBA). b) Polypropylene glycol diglycidyl ether. c) Carboxyl terminated acrylonitrile (CTBN).

Following the healing cycle and fracture of the repaired specimens, the distribution and nature of cured healing resin present on the fracture surface was investigated. Curing is highly localized and limited to the catalyst regions, as well as a small boundary region. Healing efficiency is expected to change with catalyst distribution. A summary of healing for all distributions is given in

Table 1. Distribution **B**, which features two 1.5 x 1.5 mm regions of catalyst, equivalent to 2% of the fracture surface, achieved the lowest healing efficiency at 45% ± 15%. Distribution **A** resulted in the highest mean healing efficiency of 133% ± 28%. However, the areal density of catalyst in type **B** specimens is significantly lower than in type **A**, in which catalyst covers 20% of the fracture surface. A representative example of pristine and healed behaviour of type **A** DCBs can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Representative load–displacement plot showing recovery of a type **A** embedded catalyst DCB. In this case a load recovery of 108% and fracture toughness recovery of 119% were observed.

Figure 7 shows the fracture surface of a type A DCB both before and after healing. The highly localised nature of the embedded catalyst is clear in both images. The epoxy monomer used to heal this specimen also contained a UV dye to aid observation of resin regions. Upon washing with acetone, all uncured resin is removed, leaving only regions of cured fluorescent resin.

Figure 7: A type A embedded catalyst DCB (a) before and (b) after healing with the resin described in Section 3.2, which also contained a UV dye penetrant. The localised curing of resin is illustrated in image (c), which shows only resin which could not be removed by washing with acetone.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The inclusion of a catalytic healing agent, $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$, within an oven-cured FRP and subsequent involvement of this agent in damage repair has been successfully demonstrated. The effect of catalyst inclusion on material properties has been shown to be dependent on manufacturing technique and catalyst distribution. In the case of type A cut ply specimens, in which 20% of the fracture surface is functionalised, the influence of embedded catalyst on specimen fracture energy has been shown to be within typical variation of material behaviour.

Functionalisation of as little as 15% of the fracture surface has been shown to be capable of achieving full load recovery in repaired DCBs in type E specimens. Type A specimens, however, can achieve in excess of 100% load recovery after effecting repair of 20% of the fractured area.

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